

“Vocabulary teaching methods in practical English classes of secondary schools”

Khojayeva Surayyo Abdullayevna

teacher of English at the 16th general

secondary school of Khiva, Khorezm region

Abstract: Nowadays, the problem of formation of creative abilities of teenagers in the process of teaching foreign languages is gaining special relevance. In the modern conditions of the pedagogical process of general education schools, this is an important scientific problem of historical, ethnic, cultural and socio-pedagogical importance. This article analyzes the methods of teaching vocabulary in practical English classes.

Key words: education, upbringing, adolescent, folk culture, analytical components, emotional components, creative components, song, project, language skills.

Аннотация: В настоящее время в процессе обучения иностранным языкам особую актуальность приобретает проблема формирования творческих способностей у подростков. В современных условиях педагогического процесса общеобразовательных школ это важная научная проблема историко-этнокультурного и социально-педагогического значения. В данной статье анализируются методы обучения лексике на практических занятиях по английскому языку.

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Ключевые слова: образование, воспитание, подросток, народная культура, аналитические компоненты, эмоциональные компоненты, творческие компоненты, песня, проект, языковые навыки.

Аннотация: Hozirgi kunda xorijiy tillarni o'qitish jarayonida o'spirinlarda ijodiy qobiliyatlarni shakllantirish muammosi alohida dolzarblik kasb etmoqda. Umumta'lim maktablarining pedagogik jarayonining zamonaviy sharoitida bu tarixiy, etnik, madaniy va ijtimoiy-pedagogik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan muhim ilmiy muammodir. Mazkur maqolada ingliz tili amaliy mashg'ulotlarida so'z boyligini o'rgatish usullari tahlil qilinadi.

Калит so'zlar: ta'lim, tarbiya, o'spirin, xalq mdaniyati, analitik komponentlar hissiy komponentlar, ijodiy komponentlar, qo'shiq, loyiha, til ko'nikmalari.

It is impossible to develop the creative abilities of schoolchildren without generalizing the experience of using English lessons in the education and training system. The study of the English language, its development history, national culture and everyday life is not only an activity aimed at students' learning English, but also one of the conditions that ensures the teaching of a foreign language and the development of the creative abilities of schoolchildren on concrete life material. should be considered as The formation of creative abilities in adolescents is based on the development of creative thinking, and in particular, such components as:

Analytical components - accordingly, conceptual and logical thinking - consistency, mobility, selectivity, associativeness, intelligence, ability to differentiate, etc.;

Emotional components (emotional - figurative thinking): vividness of images, emotional evaluation of events, facts, events, etc.

Creative components (visual-effective thinking): search for rational solutions, non-standard (individuality, originality, getting rid of stereotypes), the ability to predict the result, the desire to synthesize the best knowledge and skills in the activity, the ability to choose the most optimal solution from possible options and justify the correct choice. Analyzing my and my colleagues' lessons and focusing on the following conditions, I came to the conclusion that the development of creative abilities of teenagers in English language classes will be more effective.

Professional skills, the need for qualifications teacher;

high material and technical base of the school and good interaction of methodical and socio-pedagogical services;

existence of a favorable psychological microclimate at school;

trusting relationship; classes are conducted regularly and children's creative activities are guided by qualified, scientifically-based guidance;

the process of formation of creative abilities is directly related to education, knowledge and practical activity;

Pedagogical techniques, forms and methods of teaching English correspond to individual age characteristics and psychophysiological capabilities of adolescents, communication with children through games;

the use of a system of educational and creative tasks of different levels of complexity of personal and social significance aimed at the student's individuality,

his level of preparation; rejection of administrative-command forms and methods of work;

formation and development of positive personality traits (creative potential, emotional attitude, artistic taste, hard work, love for the Motherland, love for the mother tongue and other languages, respect for oneself and others, etc.), including learning English.

The teacher should guide students, contribute to the development of their creative abilities in each lesson. Only in the process of purposeful hard work, it will be possible to form certain qualities and achieve interest in the lesson. The variety of didactic work creates different purposeful attitudes in students, and the time spent on independent work increases. Acquiring knowledge, skills and competences for independent work teaches students to do creative work, develops creative thinking, creates the initial conditions for their use in the system of professional activity, improves oral and written communication skills, reflects thoughts, feelings - gives priority to the expression of feelings and emotions, and also has the ability to think. The more different tasks are used, the more effective the results will be. I would like to emphasize the following forms of work on the development of creative skills: Using songs and poems; homeworks, keeping diaries, using computer programs, defending theses and projects, business games, conferences; working with an unusually constructed text, dialogue or monologue. The students' creative activities are reflected in their hobbies. They make things from natural and other metals, love literature, keep diaries, take photos, collect collections, communicate with nature, correspond with foreign friends, unusual from ordinary and everyday things. they look for things and so on. Such hobbies can be used to increase

cognitive activity. At the request of the teacher, children bring to the lessons from their collections photos, postcards, letters, objects that enliven communication in a foreign language, this communication becomes more meaningful, close and interesting for its participants. The task of the teacher is to deeply study and know the hobbies of schoolchildren, to use them for the creative expression of students in the classroom. Currently, in the practice of teaching foreign languages in Russian schools, the project method is widely used, which introduces students to research activities, develops their creativity, independence, independence, originality of thinking. Project activity significantly expands and deepens students' knowledge in the process of working on the project, teaches them to interact with each other. where to find reliable evidence to prove it. Students use additional literature, mass media, and Internet capabilities to complete creative assignments. Having enough experience in working on projects, I would like to highlight the following work steps:

Stages of work on the project:

Stimulating, presenting situations that allow you to identify one or more problems on the topic under discussion. In other words, I provoke students to project work: I got a new apartment. Want to know something about it? Ask me a question! What do you say? Perhaps you will make a project about your apartment. (listen / speak) we activate.

Choose a project topic. Proposing hypotheses to solve the identified problem (brainstorming). Discuss and justify each of the hypotheses. At the stage, work continues with the whole class, children express their wishes, argue, propose something (forms of debate).

Practicing language skills. The teacher helps students to choose vocabulary (asking questions, indirect speech). Drafting of written material. In small groups (in each group of hypotheses), discuss testing methods based on accepted hypotheses, discuss possible sources of information for testing the hypothesis. Discuss the presentation of results. Students work in groups to write questionnaires and surveys to cover project topics (writing, speaking). Collection of information on questionnaires, interviews (giving information / writing / reading / listening).

Thus, creating problem situations in the process of working with the text ensures that students are constantly involved in independent search activities aimed at solving emerging problems, which inevitably leads to the development of knowledge independence and creative activity, and this, first of all, students affects the quality of knowledge. It is important that the student is able to apply the knowledge acquired in class, otherwise the educational process is useless.

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